

Community Radios' Broadcasting Services and Socio-Economic Development in Western Uganda: A case of Selected Communities in Mbarara District

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study was to examine how community radios' broadcasting services fostered socio-economic development in Mbarara District among communities. The objectives of the study were; 1) To examine the extent to which community radios' broadcasting services have contributed to the socio-economic development of communities in Mbarara District, Uganda, 2) To assess the effect of community radios' health broadcasting services on radio listenership among communities in Mbarara District, Uganda, 3) To analyze the relationship between community radios' listenership and socio-economic development of communities in Mbarara District, Uganda. The research design for this study was a cross sectional survey employing both quantitative and qualitative research approaches. Quantitative data was collected using questionnaires. Qualitative data was collected using both interview and FGD schedules as research instruments. The study surveyed 250 respondents and quantitative data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics; frequency distributions, cross tabulations, correlation analysis and regressions. Path analysis was lastly conducted examining the various conducted variables as a way of assessing the casual models established in the different objectives. Qualitative data analysis was done using theoretical propositions. Structural Equation Modeling was conducted to ascertain the functional relationships where a hypothesized model upon which the fitting of a structural Equation model was based. The result shows educational broadcasting ($\beta = 0.716$, $p = 0.000$. statistically significant direct effect on socio-economic development. Educational Broadcasting having a positive effect on level of participation in radio programs aired ($\beta = 0.346$, $p = 0.000$) and frequency of radio listening ($\beta = 0.174$, $p = 0.007$). Furthermore, goodness of-fit results show a Root mean squared error of approximation (RMSEA) = 0.201. This result shows a poor fit for the full model since RMSEA is greater than 0.1. Comparative Fit Index (CFI) = 0.689 is poor fit in predicting socio-economic development. In order to get a model that fits better, Structural equation modelling was again conducted. Result shows factors statistically significant indirect effect on socio-economic development of communities include; educational having a positive effect on level of participation in radio programs aired ($\beta = 0.297$, $p = 0.001$) and frequency of radio listening ($\beta = 0.187$, $p = 0.003$). This study developed a Sustainable community conscientious Operational Radio Enterprise (SCORE) Model that can be used in Community based Radios' Broadcasting Services to enhance socio-economic development among listeners.

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Introduction

It all began with the collapsing of Radio Uganda as the government owned radio by then due to lack of funds explained by the cut in budget funding by the Ministry of Information (Nsubuga, 2005). Socio-economic development in terms of literacy levels was at 69.4%, temporary housing materials in terms of mud and pole at 42.0%, and 1.9% unemployment rates (UBOS, 2006). Also, socio-economic development promoters for gender and women issues were fewest to reach the vast majority of the rural populace (Servaes, 2014). Kagadi Kibaale Community Radio was established and started by the Uganda Rural Development and Training Trust (URDTT) while Radio Apac and Mama Fm were launched in northern Uganda in the year 2001. Irrespective of the socio-economic development trends, it remained less investigated as to whether community radios contributed towards the promotion of development and to what extent which required further investigations. In order to investigate the effect of Community Radios' Broadcasting Services on Socio-Economic Development in Western Uganda, the democratic participant media theory was adopted. In its assumptions the democratic-participant media theory as contended by Enzensberger (1970) cited in McQuail (2007) has it that the promotion of self-reliance in communities was possible if the right relevant local information was broadcasted to the communities. In this way the democratic-participant media theory challenged the uniform, unified, high-cost, commercialized, professionalized that followed a majorly state-controlled media (McQuail, 2007).

Conceptual Background

A community radio was defined as one run for the community, by the community and is about community needs (Uganda's Broadcasting Policy 2011). According to UBP (2011), community radios are associated with the following prominent characteristics: -community participation in communication and airing of local community content. However, despite of these characteristics, community radios have not reasonably taken on the principle of participation of the local community in broadcasting, which is meant to empower them (Dralega, 2009). That said, community radios however, have not responded to the main concerns set by the ordinary' communities and to promote their socio-economic development plans through communication (UCC, 013).The signs of socio-economic development include demographic increases and improved health, income, educational and cultural transformations, employment rates, housing conditions and social infrastructure in addition to quality of life and environment (Harvester, 2009).In spite of the above, Poor housing conditions still stands at 56.3% in communities (Uganda Bureau of Statistics, 2016).

Contextual Background

In Mbarara District, at least 1 in every 10 households with members aged 5 years and above still consumes less than two meals (Uganda Bureau of Statistics, 2017).Unemployment surging at 17.6% in persons aged 18 years and above of working population(Uganda Bureau of Statistics, 2017)Yet Community radios have been working towards promoting socio-economic development amongst poor in rural areas (Madamombe, 2005).majority 60.3% of the households as having a radio as main source of information (Uganda Bureau of Statistics, 2016). CR have the capacity to improve the status of the rural communities (Uganda Communications Commission, 2009). This study was thus set to investigate the community radios' broadcasting services role in socio-economic development in Mbarara.

Literature Revenue

The New growth theorists particularly Romer, Lucas; Aghion as cited in Jaffee, (2012) contend that economic growth results come from increasing returns through the use of

knowledge rather than labour and capital. Al-hassan, Alhassan and Abdul-Malik (2011) found that listening to Simli Radio improved awareness and knowledge of solutions to community development problems. The authors found the improvement is not only culture and rural development but also education alongside hygiene and sanitation. Dahal and Aram, (2010) reported community radio broadcasting as being essential aspects in building a strong civil society alongside encouraging local members to express themselves. Content gaps however exist since need for clarity on what constitutes better life in the latter study. Lwanga (2011) assessed the role of community radio in promoting smaller families and family planning among Men in Uganda. The author found out that community radios' broadcasting was interactive and provided an opportunity for dialogue and feedback. Knowledge gaps exist since Lwanga's study only reports effectiveness of the program in mobilizing men.

Research Gaps

The reviewed studies on the overall shows a uniform direction that community radio broadcasting whether with regard to; health, agricultural or educational in one way or another have a bearing in as far as socio-economic development is concerned (Al-hassan et al., 2011; Kalyango, 2009; Lwanga, 2011; Lewis, 2008). However not only theoretical but also knowledge, methodological and contextual gaps exist. In the reviewed studies, knowledge gaps are equally evident as the reviewed studies fail to report on the link between community radio broadcasting and socio-economic development aspects (Muhinde, 2007; Nasunna, 2012; Meyer, 2012). Also evident in the reviewed literature are content gaps as several of the studies do not bring out clearly the different aspects of socio-economic development considered (Dahal & Aram, 2010; Hakanen, 2000; Okello, 2007).

Research Paradigm

This study adopted the Post-positivist research Paradigm because it does not only put emphasis on observable phenomena to get credible facts but also permits explanations for such observed phenomena but within a particular context. The research design for this study is a cross sectional survey employing both quantitative and qualitative research approaches. The target population of the study constituted radio listeners within the Ugandan community aged 18 years and above irrespective of the gender. The study population of the radio listeners to radio programs aired on Radio West, Vision and Endigito within the communities of Mwizi, Kamukuzi and Nyakayojo in Mbarara district. The study population size in the aforementioned communities is 732 listeners (COMNETU, 2018). The study used both probability and non-probability sampling methods of data collection since it was impractical to include the whole population. Radio west, Endigito and Vision Radio were selected for the study. The probability sampling approach code named systematic random sampling (equiprobability technique) was adopted in the selection of the radio listeners who participated in the study. The research team used a 5/10 interval pattern to select a house hold. The procedure was used because each element in the population had a known and equal probability of selection. The non-probability sampling technique specifically purposive sampling was adopted in selecting the Community Radio Personnel. According to Saunders (2012) purposive sampling is a technique of sampling where subjects for a given study are identified and selected because of the significant data they can give but which may not be got from other sources or choices. The determination of the Community Radio Listeners Sample Size was guided by Yamane's (1967). Basing on the standards of Yamane's formula, considering a 5% degree of precision at 95% confidence level and then plugging the values into the formular, the following sample size for media personnel was determined.

$$n = \frac{N}{(1+Ne^2)}$$

$$n = \frac{732}{(1+732*0.05*0.05)}$$

$$n = 258.657$$

$n \approx 259$ community radio listeners

Data collection Methods and Instruments

On media personnel, Semi-structured interviews were used, Regular radio listeners per Sub County used Quantitative survey, Village local council (L.C I), Interviews were used and On Village members Focus group discussions (FGDs) were used. For the purposes of this study, both qualitative and quantitative tools were used which including; the interview guide, questionnaire and focus group discussions (FGD) tools.

Data Quality Management

The Validity of the research instrument was tested using Content validity index (CVI). The researcher determined Validity of the research instruments, using I-CVI. The rating of items was on a 4-point ordinal scale. With a CVI of 0.842 which was higher than Lynn's recommendation of 0.70 which meant the tool was valid. The approach for this study was cronbach's Alpha coefficient. Alpha coefficient takes on any value from 0 to 1. Overall results show Cronbach Alpha Coefficient of 0.8465 which is higher than the recommended acceptable coefficient of 0.7 (Nunnally, 1978). That coefficient value was considered satisfactory for the research instrument. After data editing, coding of data was done in order to prepare data for its analysis. The coding of all raw data gathered from the field was done by preparing the study variables in a lay out that was appropriate for SPSS for data analysis purposes. The analysis of data involved both quantitative and qualitative data collected using questionnaires and interview guides respectively. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (version 23) was used for analyzing data quantitatively. SPSS aided in the coding and interpretation of data using descriptive and inferential statistics generated. Frequency tables were presented too for the univariate/single variable analysis for frequency counts. Also, the bivariate (two variable) analysis was made. The cross-tabulation analysis was done in order to understand the relationship between one or more variables and their patterns. In order to test hypotheses, Pearson correlational analysis of two variables was made. Multiple regression analyses were conducted. Path analysis was lastly conducted examining the various conducted variables as a way of assessing the casual models established in the different objectives.

Theoretical aspects of community radio services

The magic bullet or hypodermic needle theory, equates media influence with the effect of an intravenous injection with certain values, ideas and attitudes 'injected' into the media user, resulting in particular behavior (Fourie 1988). Postulates that the media tell their audience what is important and what is not in such a way that the mass media, through coverage of ideas and events, may have an influence on what the public regards as important (McCombs and Shaw 1972). Pragmatically, Kasoma (2001:29-33) contends that the need for community radio can better be appreciated against a backdrop of the technical and other shortcomings of "national radio, commercial radio, and Christian radio". Weighed against national radio, the need for community radio arises from its programing.

Table 1.0: Target Sample Size and Response rate:

Targeted Number	Administered Questionnaires	Complete responses	Response rate (%)
259	259	250	$\frac{250}{259} * 100 = 96.5\%$

Source: Primary Data, 2019

Table 1.1: Descriptive Results on Level of Community Radio Health Broadcasting

Health Broadcasting Aspects	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
Promoted campaigns against HIV/AIDS	4.37	0.97	High
Community radios brought about behaviour change to	3.89	1.28	High
Community radio promotes immunization of children	3.48	1.42	High
Community radios have promoted family planning.	3.79	0.78	High
Community radio provide sanitation and hygiene	3.49	1.43	High
Community radios support community nutrition	3.55	1.32	High
Community radios Promoted safe motherhood	3.58	1.16	High
Community radios have supported a reduction in	4.64	0.67	Very High
Community radios communicate health information	3.59	1.28	High
Promoted awareness on immunizable diseases	3.53	1.20	High
Community radios communicate health information	3.59	1.28	High
Promoted awareness on immunizable diseases	3.53	1.20	High
Promoted awareness on immunizable diseases	3.53	1.20	High

Legend: 4.20-5.00 Very High, 3.40-4.19 High, 2.60-3.39 Average, 1.80-2.59 Low, 1.00-1.79 Very Low

Table 1.1: indicates an overall high level of community radio health broadcasting among residents of communities in Mbarara District (Mean = 3.79, SD = 1.15).

Table 1.2: Descriptive Results on Level of Community Radio Agricultural Broadcasting

Agricultural Broadcasting Aspects	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
Community radio is useful in communicating agricultural information	4.24	0.84	Very High
Community radio agricultural programs are useful to agricultural extension workers	4.27	0.78	Very High
Community radios provide market information	4.20	1.04	Very High
Community radios have promoted farmers' use of findings from agricultural research institutions	4.20	0.90	Very High
Broadcast agricultural programs about training in farming	3.60	1.38	High
The community identifies with people airing agricultural programs	4.05	1.07	High
Community radios have promoted learning of better farming methods	3.46	1.41	High
Provide veterinary related information to the pastoral communities	3.27	1.32	Average
Community radios have promoted livestock keeping	4.18	0.66	High
Organize and broadcast discussions on solutions to agricultural water problems	2.97	1.36	Average
Provide information on best harvesting methods	3.64	0.93	High
Invite agricultural officials, broadcast information on new crop varieties and discussions	3.25	1.06	Average
Broadcast information on the storage and preservation of agricultural produce	3.36	1.20	Average
Broad information of forecasted weather conditions and how they affect agricultural activities	3.61	1.26	High
Broadcast crop farming needs of farmers in community	3.18	1.32	Average
Pooled Mean & Standard Deviation	3.70	1.10	High

Legend: 4.20-5.00 Very High, 3.40-4.19 High, 2.60-3.39 Average, 1.80-2.59 Low, 1.00-1.79 Very Low

Table 1.2: similarly shows an overall high level of community radio broadcasting in relation to agriculture among residents in communities in Mbarara District (Mean = 3.70, SD = 1.10).

Table 1.3: Descriptive Results on Level of Community Radio Education Broadcasting

Community Radio Education Broadcasting Aspects	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
There is promotion of cultural awareness and morals in the radio broadcasts	4.16	0.89	High
Indigenous language is promoted in the radio broadcasts	3.94	1.00	High
Moral education is promoted during the community radio broadcasts	4.42	0.88	Very High
The is promotion of religious education in Community radio broadcasts	4.01	0.83	High
Issues related to awareness on safety and security is part of the broadcasts	3.96	0.96	High
Education on the different human rights is part of the radio broadcastings	3.67	0.90	High
Education regarding political governance is part of community radio broadcasting	4.54	0.95	Very High
The Community radio broadcasts educates us on environmental protection issues like pollution, waste management, & conservation	3.98	0.85	High
Government education programs like UPE, USE and technical education are aired on the community radios	3.22	0.98	Average
Girl child education is considered in the programs broadcasts on community radio stations	3.72	1.04	High
The community radios have promoted literacy and numerical skills of the members in this community	3.20	0.99	Average
Pooled Mean & Standard Deviation	3.89	0.93	High

Legend: 4.20-5.00 Very High, 3.40-4.19 High, 2.60-3.39 Average, 1.80-2.59 Low, 1.00-1.79 Very Low

Table 1.3: above shows an overall high level of community radio broadcasting in relation to education program among residents in communities in Mbarara District (Mean = 3.89, SD = 0.93).

Table 1.4: Descriptive Results on the State of Socio-Economic Development among communities in Mbarara District

Socio Economic Development Aspects	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
The life expectancy of the community members have improved	3.82	1.06	High
As a household we have witnessed an increase in the incomes that we earn	3.38	1.31	Average
Literacy levels have improved amongst my family members	3.04	1.36	Average
Most community members have got employment of quality	3.93	1.00	High
The housing conditions have improved amongst us as community members	3.28	1.34	Average
Social amenities and infrastructure are developed and readily accessible in the community	3.13	1.27	Average
As a family our standard of living has greatly improved	3.77	1.18	High
Pooled Mean & Standard Deviation	3.48	1.22	High

Legend: 4.20-5.00 Very High, 3.40-4.19 High, 2.60-3.39 Average, 1.80-2.59 Low, 1.00-1.79 Very Low

Table 1.4: shows on the aggregate a high level of Socio-Economic Development among communities in Mbarara District (Mean = 3.48, SD = 1.22).

Table 1.5: Correlational Matrix for the Relationship between Community Radio Broadcasting and Socio-Economic Development of Communities in Mbarara District

Correlations		Socio Economic Health Broadcast	Agric Broadcast	Educational Broadcasting
Socio Economic Devt	Pearson Correlation	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)			
	N	250		
Health Broadcast	Pearson Correlation	-.002	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.975		
	N	250	250	
Agric Broadcast	Pearson Correlation	.119	.152*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.061	.016	
	N	250	250	250
Educational Broadcasting	Pearson Correlation	.399**	.173**	.222**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.006	.000
	N	250	250	250

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 1.5: Indicates Health broadcasting ($r = -.002$, $p = 0.975$), agricultural broadcasting ($r = 0.119$, $p = 0.061$), educational broadcasting ($r = 0.399$, $p = 0.000$)

Table 1.6: Regression Results on the effect of Community Radio Broadcasting on Socio-Economic Development of Communities in Mbarara District

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.522	.586		.890	.374
Health Broadcasting	-.108	.083	-.078	-1.308	.192
Agricultural Broadcasting	.080	.116	.041	.685	.494
Educational Broadcasting	.789	.118	.403	6.674	.000
R^2	0.166				
Adj. R^2	.155				
F	16.276				
P Value	.000				

a. Dependent Variable: Socio Economic Development

Table 1.6 show that health, agricultural and educational broadcasting explained 15.5% of the variation in socio-economic development of communities (adjusted $R^2 = 0.155$).84.5% of the variation was accounted for by other factors not considered under this model. Educational Broadcasting ($\beta = 0.403$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$) had a statistically positive effect on Socio-Economic Development of Communities of Mbarara District. This is sufficient evidence that there is significant relationship exists between community radio education broadcasting and socio-economic development of communities.

Table 2.0: Community Radios' Listenership among Residents in Mbarara District

Radios' Listenership and Participation Aspects		Frequency (N = 250)	Percentage (%)
Frequency of Radio Listening	Very Rarely	7	2.8
	Rarely	28	11.2
	Often	151	60.4
	Very Often	64	25.6
Belong to radio listening groups	Yes	178	71.2
	No	72	28.8
Community radio program most preferred	Religious	22	8.8
	Entertainment	48	19.2
	Health	91	36.4
	Agricultural	89	35.6
Community radio programs' participation	Yes	102	40.8
	No	148	59.2

Source: Primary data, 2019

Table 2.0 shows that most of the Residents in Mbarara District often listen to the program broadcasted on the different community radios 151(60.4%). Health related programs 91(36.4%), agricultural related programs 89(35.6%), entertainment program (19.2%) religious programs listening at 22(8.8%).

Table 2.1: Correlational Results between Extent of Community Radio Broadcasting and Radios' Listenership

Correlations		Participation	Listening group membership	Listening frequency	Health Broadcast	Agric Broadcast	Educ Broadcast
Participation	Correlation Coefficient	1.000					
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.					
	N	250					
Listening group member	Correlation Coefficient	-.263**	1.000				
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.				
	N	250	250				
CR listening frequency	Correlation Coefficient	.007	-.180**	1.000			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.918	.004	.			
	N	250	250	250			
Health Broadcast	Correlation Coefficient	-.101	-.117	.154*	1.000		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.110	.064	.015	.		
	N	250	250	250	250		
Agric Broadcast	Correlation Coefficient	-.009	-.050	.037	.140*	1.000	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.888	.434	.561	.027	.	
	N	250	250	250	250	250	
Educ Broadcast	Correlation Coefficient	.227**	-.022	.175**	.174**	.223**	1.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.724	.006	.006	.000	.
	N	250	250	250	250	250	250

Source: Primary data, 2019

Table 2.1 shows weak negative insignificant relationship between agricultural broadcasting and community radio participation among community residents ($r = -0.009$, $p = 0.888$). Results equally show that agricultural broadcasting is neither correlated with Listening group membership ($r = -0.050$, $p = 0.434$), nor frequency of listening demonstrated among residents ($r = 0.037$, $p = 0.250$). Table 6.2 indicates a weak negative insignificant correlation between health broadcasting and community radio participation ($r = -.101$, $p = 0.110$). However, shows a weak positive but statistically significant correlation between health broadcasting and frequency of radio listening ($r = 0.154$, $p = 0.015$).

Also shows a weak positive but statistically significant correlation between educational broadcasting and community radio participation ($r = 0.227$, $p = 0.000$).

Table 2.2: Regression Results for the effect of Community Radio Broadcasting on Participation

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
(Constant)	-.157	.456		-.345	.730
Health Broadcasting	-.123	.064	-.121	-1.909	.057
Agricultural Broadcasting	-.085	.090	-.060	-.942	.347
Educational Broadcasting	.346	.092	.241	3.763	.000
R^2	0.062				
$Adj. R^2$	0.050				
F	5.410				
$P Value$	0.001				

a. Dependent Variable: Level of Participation

Source: Primary data, 2019

Table 2.2 shows that community radio broadcasting namely; health, agricultural and educational broadcasting explained 5% of the variation in the level of participation (adjusted $R^2 = 0.050$). 95% of the variation was accounted for by other factors not considered under this model. One form of community radio broadcasting that's Education ($\beta = 0.241$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$) had a statistically positive effect on level of participation demonstrated by residents.

There is sufficient evidence that significant relationship exists between one of the aspects of community radio broadcasting and radio listenership among communities.

Table 2.3: Regression Results for the effect of Community Radio Broadcasting on Listenership Group Membership

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
(Constant)	.989	.430		2.302	.022
Health Broadcasting	-.110	.061	-.118	-1.821	.070
Agricultural Broadcasting	-.052	.085	-.040	-.607	.544
Educational Broadcasting	.086	.087	.065	.988	.324
R^2	0.017				
$Adj. R^2$	0.005				
F	1.440				
$P Value$	0.232				

a. Dependent Variable: Listenership Group Membership

Source: Primary data, 2019

Table 2.3 shows that community radio broadcasting namely; health, agricultural and educational broadcasting explained 0.5% of the variation in the level of participation (adjusted $R^2 = 0.005$). But are not significant predictors in the extent of group membership ($F = 1.440$, $P = 0.232$). The results show that neither of the different forms of community radio broadcasting have a significant effect on extent to which residents belonged to listening groups.

Table 2.4: Regression Results for the effect of Community Radio Broadcasting on Frequency of Radio Listening

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	-.014	.324		-.042	.966
Health Broadcasting	.088	.046	.123	1.928	.055
Agricultural Broadcasting	-.037	.064	-.037	-.581	.562
Educational Broadcasting	.174	.065	.172	2.665	.008
R^2	0.049				
Adj. R^2	0.037				
F	4.219				
P Value	0.006				

a. Dependent Variable: Radio Listening Frequency

Source: Primary data, 2019

Table 2.4 shows that community radio broadcasting namely; health, agricultural and educational broadcasting explained 3.7% of the variation in the level of participation (adjusted $R^2 = 0.037$). This means that 96.3% of the variation was accounted for by other factors not considered under this model. Results show that only educational broadcasting by community radios ($\beta = 0.172$, $p = 0.008 < 0.05$) had a significant positive effect on frequency of listening to radio programs. There is thus adequate evidence that significant relationship exists between at least one of the aspects of community radio broadcasting and frequency of listenership among communities.

Table 2.5: Correlational Results between Radios' Listenership and Socio-Economic Development

Correlations		Socio Economic Participation Devt	Listening group CR	listening frequency
Socio Economic Devt	Correlation Coefficient	1.000		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.		
	N	250		
Participation	Correlation Coefficient	.191**	1.000	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	.	
	N	250	250	
Listening group membership	Correlation Coefficient	.062	-.263**	1.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.325	.000	.
	N	250	250	250
CR Listening Frequency	Correlation Coefficient	.061	.007	-.180**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.338	.918	.004
	N	250	250	250

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Primary data, 2019

The results in Table 2.5 indicate a very weak positive insignificant correlation between belonging to a listenership group and level of socio-economic development ($r = 0.062$, $p = 0.325$). A weak positive insignificant correlation was found between frequency of radio listening and level of socio-economic development among communities ($r = 0.061$, $p = 0.338$). However, it shows a weak positive significant relationship between participation in radio programs and level of socio-economic development among communities ($r = 0.191$, $p = 0.002$).

Table 2.6: Regression Results for the effect of Radio Listenership on Socio-Economic Development

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	3.031	.152		19.925	.000
Participation	.266	.088	.195	3.030	.003
Listening group membership	.220	.097	.148	2.264	.024
Radio Listening Frequency	.211	.122	.109	1.731	.005
R^2	0.051				
Adj. R^2	.040				
F	4.431				
P Value	0.005				

a. Dependent Variable: Socio Economic Development

The findings in Table 2.6 show that radio listenership namely; participation, belonging to listening group and radio listening frequency explained 4% of the variation in socio-economic development (adjusted $R^2 = 0.040$). This means that 96% of the variation was accounted for by other factors not considered under this model. The different aspects of radio listenership that's participation, belonging to listening group and radio listening frequency are significant predictors of socio-economic development ($F = 4.431$, $p = 0.005$). The hypothesis that states an insignificant relationship between radio listenership and socio-economic development of communities is rejected.

Functional relationship between the variables

The study having established that Community Radio Broadcasting influences both Socio-Economic Development of communities and yet Radio Listenership significantly influences on the Socio-Economic Development, Structural Equation Modeling was conducted to ascertain the functional relationships. It is a Hypothesized model upon which the fitting of a structural Equation model was based.

Figure 7.1: Hypothesized SEM model for the functional relationship between community radio broadcasting, listenership and Socio Economic Development

Table 3.0: Coefficient and Standard Error of the Final SEM Model of Socio-Economic Development Influencing Factors in Communities of Mbarara District

Variables	Coefficient	S.E.	Sig.	95% C.I Lower	Upper
Direct Effects					
Socio Economic Development					
Health Broadcasting	-.083	.083	0.322	-.246	.0801
Agricultural Broadcasting	.102	.115	0.377	-.124	.327
Educational Broadcasting	.716	.123	0.000	.474	.957
Participation	.139	.085	0.101	-.027	.305
Listening group membership	.139	.092	0.129	-.040	.318
Radio listening frequency	.078	.1156	0.500	-.149	.305
Indirect Effects					
Participation 0 1					
Health Broadcasting	-.123	.064	0.054	-.248	.002
Agricultural Broadcasting	-.085	.089	0.342	-.261	.091
Educational Broadcasting	.346	.091	0.000	.167	.525
Listening group membership					
Health Broadcasting	-.110	.060	0.066	-.228	.007
Agricultural Broadcasting	-.052	.085	0.540	-.218	.114
Educational Broadcasting	.086	.086	0.319	-.083	.254
CR listening freq					
Health Broadcasting	.088	.045	0.052	-.001	.177
Agricultural Broadcasting	-.037	.065	0.558	-.162	.088
Educational Broadcasting	.174	.065	0.007	-.643	.616

SEM structural equation modeling, SEM model endogenous variables are Radio Listenership Characteristics; exogenous variables are Community Radio Broadcasting, CI confidence interval

Table 3.0 shows educational broadcasting ($\beta = 0.716, p = 0.000$. statistically significant direct effect on socio-economic development. Educational Broadcasting having a positive effect on level of participation in radio programs aired ($\beta = 0.346, p = 0.000$) and frequency of radio listening ($\beta = 0.174, p = 0.007$).

Full SEM model of the Socio-Economic Development influencing Factors in Communities of Mbarara District

Table 3.1: Goodness-of-fit statistics for the Full SEM Model of the Socio-Economic Development influencing Factors in Communities of Mbarara District

Goodness-of-fit statistics	Value
Root mean squared error of approximation	0.201, 95% CI (0.143–0.265)
Pclose	0.000, < 0.05
Comparative fit index (CFI)	0.689
Tucker-Lewis index (TLI)	-0.868
Standardized root mean squared residual (SRMSR)	0.058
Coefficient of determination (CD)	0.242

Table 3.1 shows a Root mean squared error of approximation (RMSEA) = 0.201. This result shows a poor fit for the full model since RMSEA is greater than 0.1. Comparative Fit Index (CFI) = 0.689 is poor fit in predicting socio-economic development. In order to get a model that fits better, Structural equation modelling was again conducted. Table 8.3, shows factors statistically significant indirect effect on socio-economic development of communities include; educational having a positive effect on level of participation in radio programs aired ($\beta = 0.297, p = 0.001$) and frequency of radio listening ($\beta = 0.187, p = 0.003$). The paths for the reduced fitted model are as illustrated in Figure below.

Reduced SEM model of the Socio-Economic Development influencing Factors in Communities of Mbarara District

Contribution to new knowledge

During the study the following gaps were identified; the reviewed studies showed that knowledge gaps are equally evident as they fail to report on the link between community radio broadcasting and socio-economic development aspects (Muhinde, 2007; Nasunna, 2012; Meyer, 2012). Also evident in the reviewed literature are content gaps as several of the studies do not bring out clearly the different aspects of socio-economic development considered (Dahal & Aram, 2010; Hakanen, 2000; Okello, 2007) Methodological gaps as none of the reviewed studies bring out the mediating functional relationships borne of community broadcasting yet some of the reviewed studies made use of qualitative methods yet they are borne of subjectivity syndrome let alone the limiting aspect of representativeness. (Mchakulu, 2007; Khalil & Osman, 2009; Sisya, 2003). Therefore, basing on the above gaps, this study developed a Sustainable community conscientious Operational Radio Enterprise (SCORE) Model that can be used in Community based Radios’ Broadcasting Services to enhance socio-economic development among listeners.

Sustainable conscientious Operational Radio Enterprise (SCORE) Model Operationalization on SCORE model

Licensed community Radios in Mbarara

Conclusion

It was recognized that both variables were mediated by radio listenership behavior. The total casual effect of Community Radios' Broadcasting Services on Socio-Economic Development was determined by use of a path analysis method as a result a reduced structural equation modeling was conducted and Educational broadcasting services were statistically found significantly affecting the level of socio-economic development among the communities. Furthermore, a hypothetical model was used to establish whether Community Radios' Broadcasting Services could affect Socio-Economic Development in western Uganda. This revealed that there is a relationship between Community Radios' Broadcasting Services and Socio-Economic Development.

Recommendations

The community radios' services will make more impact if the communities take a more active part in the communication processes. The Community radio leaders need to adopt a more entrepreneurial approach in the operation of radio stations. This is important in increasing listenership and ultimately more sponsors of the programs wanting to secure relevant content on air. At least in the areas that community radios work or reach, it will be very helpful if listening to the radio programs if is rewarding and motivating. Furthermore, there is a need to collect feedback from the communities in time that may improve on the content quality. Also, some editions of community radio programs would need to be interactive and issue based involving phoning in and script writing competitions. Additionally, the development of an entertainment and education programs that focuses on HIV/AIDS, Malaria, and other health concerns would greatly strengthen the health programming of community radios, since HIV and Malaria were identified in the study as one of the most prevalent diseases impacting the socio-economic development of the studied communities. Finally, since community radio is by the community for the community and managed by community, Uganda Communications Commission (UCC) should enforce the broadcasting policy of September, 2004.

Areas for further research

The study recommends that further research be conducted on the same study but with a larger sample of community radios. It further recommends similar research but on different types of radio stations for example public and commercial radio stations. Also, a similar study should be conducted to pursue this study's hypotheses but using other reputable community development survey instruments and other research methodologies to determine if the

findings and conclusion of this research can be affirmed by other approaches to add depth to our knowledge of this subject. A new study may also be done on the same variables; community radios' broadcasting and socio-economic development but, the variables may be interchanged or swapped in that socio-economic development becomes the independent variable and community radios' broadcasting, becomes the outcome variable. In addition, a study should be conducted about the Impact of ICTs on effectiveness of Community Radio Broadcasting.

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